

**Flight Training Perceptions:
Flight Students' Perception of Risks in Flight Training**

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Abstract

This paper will discuss the dangers of flight training, specifically how flight students and flight instructors perceive those dangers. As will be discussed in more detail later, the top causes of accidents in flight training are loss of control on landing, unintended stalls, fuel mismanagement, mechanical failure, and mid-air collisions. However, these top five dangers vary significantly in the percentage of accidents caused. This paper will examine the perceived greatest dangers by students and instructors and compare them to what proper research indicates are the most significant risks. This aims to answer the question: How do participants in flight training, including students and certified flight instructors (CFIs), perceive risk in flight training, and how does that perception compare to incidents that actually occur during flight training? This question is essential to answer because student pilots should train for the more likely dangers more often, so that they can stay safe. This question will be answered through a survey that was given to a variety of student pilots and CFIs.

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Introduction

Flying in an airplane is inherently a dangerous activity. While most people who know anything about aviation will say that aviation is the safest form of transport, there is more opportunity for harm to people and property when hurtling through the sky than cruising along on the ground. So how is it that something so dangerous in itself becomes the safest form of transport? It is due to the numerous safety regulations and standards, especially those that must be met to obtain the certification required for operating aircraft. So, then one must wonder, does that make flight training dangerous? Moreover, more importantly, how do those involved in the flight training see the risks of flight training, and do they work to mitigate them? Do those in flight training focus on learning how to overcome the dangers that they are most likely to encounter? These questions will be addressed later in this paper.

Danger in aviation often seems to be a priority in research, as it is an industry that is often perceived as much more hazardous than it actually is. Therefore, it would seem that many research projects would focus on the dangers of flight training, as learning to fly a plane may seem inherently risky, especially in a society that overestimates the dangers of flying in general. However, there are relatively few research studies that focus specifically on dangers within flight training. The studies that do focus on this topic provide valuable information that seems to agree, but there is not as much research on the subject as one might expect. Additionally, research on flight students' perceptions of risk in flight training is scarce. This seems counterintuitive because the perception of flight students in flight training could have a big impact on flight training.

It might seem to some that the flight students' perspective on flight training dangers should not matter, given that the flight instructor ultimately decides what flight students cover in training and often instructs them on what to study. However, if a student perceives a certain risk as more important than another, they might pay more attention when learning and studying that risk, and they might gloss over something that they perceive as not being an issue. So, it is important to look at the perspective of flight students, because what pilots perceive as high risk is likely to be what they are most prepared for, especially in a scenario, such as flight training, where the pilot is not going to be able to immediately be prepared for whatever scenario could happen.

Understanding the dangers of flight training is crucial for everyone within the aviation industry, as a proper understanding of these dangers is necessary to effectively address them and thereby mitigate their likelihood. If flight training becomes too dangerous, it discourages new pilots from starting their training. Therefore, it is essential to identify the most critical aspects of in-flight training and focus on those during training. To examine these aspects, this research paper investigated how flight students perceive the likelihood of different risks in flight training becoming accidents, and how that compares to recorded accidents in flight training. The paper also explored how flight students perceive the likelihood of different risks in flight training becoming fatalities, and how that compares to recorded accidents in flight training.

Literature Review

Previous studies have not investigated flight students' perspectives on the potential incidents and accidents that can occur during flight training. This research, however, relies on previous studies that have examined the likelihood of incidents occurring in flight training, the possibility that specific incidents lead to more severe problems, and research on the safety of flight training specifically, as opposed to the broader field of general aviation. The closest previous study to this research is *Exploring Collegiate Flight Training Students' Perceptions of Safety Culture*, which examined flight training students at a specific university and their perceptions of safety culture. This study found that students have a favorable view of the safety culture when the administration in charge effectively communicates its commitment to safety. Additionally, students have a more positive outlook on the safety culture when those in charge demonstrate that they are actively involved in ensuring safety (Anderson et al., 2024). Although this previous research may not have direct application to this paper, as it focuses on the perception of culture rather than the perception of the risks, it does demonstrate that students are involved in and interested in the safety of flight training, which is a crucial factor in mitigating the risks involved in flight training. There is a limited focus on safety considerations for specifically flight training within the general aviation industry (Lekea et al., 2022). So, previous research does not talk much about the specific topic that this research paper is focused on; however, previous studies provide a foundation on the subject of safety and danger within flight training, which is needed in order to effectively understand the perceptions that flight students have about the risks associated with flight training.

Likelihood of Having Accidents or Fatalities in Flight Training

Training might seem like the most dangerous type of flight, given that pilots with little to no experience are at the controls, but research suggests otherwise. According to one study, instructional flights for fixed-wing aircraft have fewer accidents than non-instructional general aviation flights, and the fatality rate for all instructional flights is about half that of non-instructional general aviation flights (AOPA, 2014). Meaning that there is a relatively low likelihood of accidents happening in flight training, and flight training is relatively safe in comparison to other activities within the scope of general aviation. For the accidents that do occur during flight training, they are categorized into two areas: primary training and advanced training, as well as between student pilot solo flights and dual instruction. Approximately two-thirds of flight training accidents happen during the primary flight training, yet two-thirds of the fatal flight training accidents happen during advanced flight training; additionally, for primary flight training, approximately two-thirds of accidents that occur are during student solo flights, while two-thirds of the fatal accidents are during dual-instruction (AOPA, 2014). This data is interesting because, while it might be expected that the flight training of students who are not yet pilots would cause more accidents than the advanced training of already certified pilots, it shows that the accidents of the primary flight training are more likely to be survivable. Overall, flight training is not inherently dangerous. Although the perceptions of specific risks may not yet be fully understood, flight students appear to have a generally favorable view of the safety culture within their flight training. Students, in general, are not afraid of flying, but they need to be aware of the dangers present in order to avoid them.

Most Significant Accident Causes in Flight Training

To ensure the safety of flight training, students need to understand the specific risks that may affect them. To understand which risks pose the greatest danger, it is helpful to examine the factors that often lead to accidents. According to a report released by the FAA, the most common cause of crashes during flight training is loss of control on landing (Baker et al., 1996). Research from AOPA reached a similar conclusion, stating that half of all accidents that occur during dual instruction training flights, and 80 percent of those that occur during primary training students' solo flights, happen during takeoff, landing, or go-around, with the majority of these incidents occurring during landing (AOPA, 2014). Research based in Australia also found that landing caused the highest number of accidents, accounting for approximately two-thirds of accidents in student solo flights (Lekea et al., 2022). According to the FAA report, after loss of control on landing, which during the period of their report caused 36 percent of accidents. The following are the highest causes of accidents: stalls, accounting for 15 percent of accidents; fuel starvation, at 12 percent; mechanical failure, at 13 percent; and midair collisions, at 3 percent (Baker et al., 1996). Similarly, AOPA research identifies the causes of accidents after takeoff, landing, and go-around as stalls, followed by fuel mismanagement, and then mechanical and engine failure (AOPA, 2014). These reports align in their assessment of the order of causes of accidents in flight training, despite being conducted several decades apart. This alignment suggests that the information they found is accurate and has not undergone significant changes. Additionally, both studies show that loss of control during landing is the most common, with a significant drop-off in the percentage for the other causes. Furthermore, they both indicate a substantial decline in the percentage of mechanical failures and other individual causes of accidents. However, the most

common causes of accidents did not necessarily cause the most fatal accidents. Of the common causes, while landing was the most accident-inducing, it resulted in the least number of fatalities. The most fatalities were caused by mechanical failures, followed by stalls, then mid-air collisions, and then fuel mismanagement, with loss of control on landing being the least fatal (AOPA, 2014). Student pilots must be aware of what causes high numbers of accidents, and what causes the most dangerous accidents, because it is up to the individual student to study any emergency procedure that he may not be proficient in, and so focus should be spent on learning to avoid accidents that may be most likely to be encountered.

Safety Considerations For Student Pilots

Flight students should strive to avoid situations that could lead to an accident or incident. While there are a few causes that are most likely to cause accidents, there are more things that student pilots should be aware of to avoid, in order to maintain safety. One of the most serious and prominent issues in aviation is fatigue; flying while tired causes numerous problems, and students often do not get sufficient rest. Therefore, it is essential that student pilots learn about fatigue in order to mitigate the risks (Rutledge et al., 2025). While fatigue is not one of the primary causes of accidents in flight training, it can still pose significant issues during and after flight training. Therefore, it is essential for students to understand the dangers of fatigue in flight. Fatigue risk management within a safety management system can help mitigate the risks associated with fatigued pilots causing accidents, so fatigue risk management systems should be implemented by flight training institutions (Rutledge et al., 2025). While it is not required for institutions to implement such programs, they are beneficial programs to have, because they teach students how to stay safe from issues that may arise. The same idea can be applied to other

things, so that students are not put in a position where they are not safe if it is not safe for them to do so. Another factor that can lead to accidents or make them more problematic is a lack of knowledge on how to handle emergencies. It is important for a flight student to be well-versed in responding to emergency situations. Physical and in-person systems for this training may not always be available and practical, so the development and implementation of virtual tools for flight safety procedures training would be significant (Lekea et al., 2022). Flight students should focus on learning to react appropriately to emergency situations, and one way to do that is by exploring how they can utilize their personal devices as training aids. Furthermore, in training, the more that is learned, the safer it becomes, usually. While IFR (Instrument Flight Rating) certification can reduce the risk of accidents due to terrain, obstacles, and spatial disorientation, it can also increase the likelihood of accidents caused by equipment malfunction (Shao et al., 2014). It is essential in training not to become overly reliant on equipment, as it is crucial to be able to work effectively without it when something goes wrong. Overall, training is a relatively safe environment. The training environment is safe due to the instructor's close supervision of the student, the extra attention to safety procedures, and the repeated practice inherent in the flight training environment (Walach, 2023). This safety might be translated to safety in flying beyond training by continuing to practice often and paying attention to safety procedures, even when they seem natural, because becoming complacent can lead to safety hazards. Therefore, flight training is safe, but to maintain this safety, flight students must maintain a proper perspective on the risks inherent to flying.

Methodology

Participants

The participants in this study were all aviation students pursuing flight certificates and/or ratings. Due to the limited time and resources available for this research, a convenience sample was used, consisting of college students from California Baptist University only. The research was conducted using an online survey, with every respondent answering the same ten questions. The survey was anonymous, not recording personally identifiable characteristics such as name, sex, age, ethnicity, or religion. Respondents to this survey were not compensated in any way. Respondents were invited to participate through a QR code and a link, either via personal interaction with the researcher (in person or online) or by interacting with individuals who had already completed the survey and retained a link or QR code to share with others. Due to the confined sample, the research may likely be reasonably generalized to students at California Baptist University, but not to flight students in general.

Materials

This research was conducted via an online survey. Appendix A contains the text of the survey given to respondents. The survey was completed on the respondent's individual device, either a phone or a laptop. In the survey, respondents ranked five different flight hazards across three categories: likelihood of occurrence, danger level in occurrence, and importance in preparation. The survey also asked respondents whether they believed accidents were more or less likely and more or less fatal during instructional flights compared to non-instructional flights. The survey asked respondents to rank the importance of a pre-flight safety self-assessment for both Certified Flight Instructors (CFIs) and student pilots.

Design

The survey was designed to yield quantitative data. The questions were all multiple-choice or rank-choice question types, which may have limited the specific responses that respondents could provide, but this made the data analyzable for the purpose of this research. The central portion of the survey ranks the variables of the five highest causes of accidents in flight training, being loss of control during takeoff and landing, stalls, fuel mismanagement, mechanical failure, and midair collisions in relation to the likelihood of causing an accident, danger in the event of an accident, and importance to prepare for during training. Additionally, the survey analyzed and categorized the responses into two groups: primary flight students (those pursuing a private pilot's license) and advanced student pilots (those holding a private pilot's license and pursuing additional ratings).

Procedure

Upon scanning the QR code or clicking the link to the survey, respondents would be directed to a survey page that included the survey title and a brief informed consent statement, which they had to agree to in order to begin the survey. The first two questions were, whether the person was from CBU or a different flight training institution, and if they were a CFI or a flight student (this was because the original plan was for a broader participant pool, but that turned out not to be feasible). The survey then asked flight students what level of training they were currently pursuing. Respondents were then asked to respond to the survey questions as previously explained. The survey did not require every answer to be completed in order to submit the survey; however, all respondents who submitted the survey answered every question.

Results

This section presents the results based on survey findings¹. Raw data can be found in Appendix B.

Perception of Instructional v. Non-instructional Flights

The research found that respondents believed that accidents are more likely to happen during instructional flights than during non-instructional flights. As shown in Table 1, when asked whether instructional or non-instructional flights would cause more accidents, 67 percent of respondents chose the “More likely during instructional flights” option.

Table 1

Perceived likelihood of accidents in instructional versus non-instructional flights

Do you believe accidents are more likely to happen during instructional or non-instructional flights?	Percentage of Respondents	Number of Respondents
More likely during instructional	67.2%	39
More likely during non-instructional	32.8%	19

In the research, respondents said that they believe accidents would be more fatal during non-instructional flights. When asked if the thought instructional or non-instructional flight accidents would be more likely to be fatal, 57% responded that non-instructional flight accidents would be more fatal.

¹ Data analysis and graph making was assisted by Microsoft Copilo (Microsoft, 2025)

Table 2

Perception of accident fatality in instructional versus non-instructional flights

Do you believe accidents are more likely to be fatal during instructional or non-instructional flights?	Percentage of Respondents	Number of Respondents
More fatal during instructional	43.1%	33
More fatal during non-instructional	56.9%	25

Perception of the Importance of Pre-flight Self-Assessments

When asked to rank the importance of a CFI performing a pre-flight self-assessment, 100 percent of respondents ranked it as “very important,” which was the highest importance ranking available. When asked to rank the importance of a student pilot performing a pre-flight self-assessment, as stated in Table 3, most, 64 percent, ranked it as “very important,” while some ranked it as “important,” 26 percent, or “neutral,” 10 percent.

Table 3

Perception of pre-flight self-assessment importance for student pilots

How important is it for a student pilot to complete a pre-flight self-assessment?	Percentage of Respondents	Number of Respondents
Very Important	63.8%	37
Important	25.9%	15
Neutral	10.3%	6

Perceptions of Accident Causes

To look at the perception of flight training accident causes, Figure 1 looks at the average rank of the five main accident causes in each of the three different categories: most likely to cause an

accident, most dangerous if it causes an accident, and most important to prepare for. A cause for an accident being ranked as one is most (dangerous, likely, or important to prepare for), and being ranked five is least (dangerous, likely, or important to prepare for). Which means that in Figure 1, the bar that stretches the furthest down is the least in whichever category, and the bar that is the shortest is the most in the category. For example, the longest blue bar denotes that midair collisions were ranked as the least likely to cause an accident, and the shortest green bar denotes that unintended stalls were ranked as the most important to prepare for.

Figure 1

Average ranks of accident causes (1 being most, 5 being least)

Figures 2, 3, and 4 will look solely at the percentages of respondents who ranked each accident cause as the number one most likely in each category. It is important to note that Figure 1 presents the average of all rankings for each category, while Figures 2, 3, and 4 focus solely on the number ranked as number one, which may yield seemingly different results. For example,

Figure 1 shows that the loss of control on landing and stalls have a very close average rating in terms of the likelihood of causing an accident. In contrast, Figure 2 illustrates a notable difference within the same category. Figure 2 shows the percentage of respondents who chose each accident-causing hazard as the most likely to cause an accident during flight training. Most respondents ranked the loss of control on landing as their first most likely cause of an accident, out of the available options. The next most popular choice, for the category most likely to cause an accident, was an unintended stall. A small percentage of people stated that fuel mismanagement would be the most likely cause of an accident, and no respondent identified mechanical failure or mid-air collision as the most likely cause of an accident.

Figure 2

Percent of respondents who ranked each accident cause as #1 most likely to occur

Figure 3 shows the percentage of respondents who chose each accident-causing hazard as the most dangerous in the event that it does cause an accident during flight training. The highest percent of respondents ranked mechanical failure as the most dangerous, followed by loss of control on landing, then midair collision, then unintended stall, and no respondent ranked fuel mismanagement as the most dangerous. In Figure 3, the highest percentage of respondents is less than half, whereas Figure 2 shows that over half of the respondents agree with one of the answers.

Figure 3

Percent of respondents who ranked each accident cause as #1 most dangerous if it causes an accident

Figure 4 shows the percentage of respondents who chose each accident-causing hazard as the most important to prepare for during flight training. The highest percentage of respondents

ranked unintended stalls as the most important factor to prepare for, followed by loss of control on landing, then mechanical failure, and fuel mismanagement. No respondents ranked midair collisions as the most important factor to prepare for. Unintended stalls and loss of control on landing have similar percentages of respondents choosing them as their top priority, followed closely by mechanical failure and fuel mismanagement, which also have similar numbers of respondents ranking them as their top priority.

Figure 4

Percent of respondents who ranked each accident cause as #1 most important to prepare for

In most questions, the private pilot students and the non-private pilot students provided very close answers, and thus their differences were not significant. However, in the responses to one question, a significant difference was observed. This was the question that asked which accident cause was the most important to prepare for. Figure 5 shows that private pilots identify either

unintended stalls or loss of control on landing as the most significant hazards to prepare for, with over 60 percent of private pilot students citing unintended stalls as their primary concern. Moreover, it shows that non-private pilot students, or those seeking more advanced ratings, consider loss of control on landing as the most important hazard to prepare for, followed by mechanical failure and unintended stalls at nearly the same percentage, and then fuel mismanagement as the least important.

Figure 5

How private pilot students v. advanced student respondents ranked each accident cause as #1 most important to prepare for

Conclusion

A goal of this research was to determine how student pilots perceive the risk involved in flight training and how their perceptions compare to data that has been recorded regarding flight training. The previous studies mentioned earlier showed that instructional flights are less likely to cause accidents and less likely to cause fatalities than non-instructional flights (AOPA, 2014), and Table 2 showed that student pilots had the right idea as it pertained to fatalities not as likely to happen during flight training; however, Table 1 showed that flight students believe that accidents are more likely to happen during training. This is an interesting finding because it suggests that flight students perceive flight training as more dangerous than it actually is. If flight students, who already know about aviation, believe flight training to be more dangerous than it is, then it may imply that people in a similar situation who are not receiving flight training might choose not to be a part of flight training due to the perceived risk of an accident that is not as prominent as people may think.

When examining the top hazards that can cause accidents in flight training, the responses aligned with the data found. Figure 2 shows that most students see loss of control on landing as the most likely to cause an accident, and Figure 3 shows that most students see mechanical failure as the most dangerous; these answers align with what studies showed to be the case for both of these categories (AOPA, 2014; Baker et al., 1996). This suggests that, in general, the flight students surveyed appear to receive good instruction on safety hazards to be aware of. This may be because flight students surveyed study at a collegiate Part 141 flight school, which often provides stricter and more complete classroom-type education than the Part 61 flight schools. One interesting point, however, is that according to survey respondents, the second most

dangerous hazard in the event of an accident is loss of control on landing, when the studies actually put loss of control on landing as one of the lowest in causing injury or fatality, and after mechanical failure, put stalls as the next most likely to cause injury or fatality; the survey respondents ranked stalls second least dangerous. This is interesting because it implies that flight students perceive loss of control on landing to be a bigger risk than it really is, which could be because when a student imagines loss of control on landing, they might imagine crashing into the ground at highspeed, whereas it is more likely for students to be at low speeds near the ground, and whatever error they make causes accident, but their low speed and vicinity to an airport allows it to be a much less dangerous accident than student pilots expect.

The most interesting result from the survey is the responses regarding the importance of preparing for various hazards that can cause accidents. This is for two reasons: first, there is no data to indicate a correct or incorrect answer, and secondly, it is the only survey answer with significantly different responses from students pilots in their initial private pilot training, and from students in more advanced training. Private pilot students believed that unintended stalls were the most important to prepare for, followed by loss of control on landing. In contrast, more advanced students considered loss of control on landing to be the most important aspect to prepare for, followed by unintended stalls, mechanical failure, and fuel mismanagement. Students may put stalls first because it is an emergency procedure practiced frequently in flight training. One clear reason to put loss of control first is that it is also considered the most likely scenario to cause an accident, meaning they are preparing for the most likely scenario. Both of these answers seem reasonable in this scenario, but advanced students may prioritize preparing for stalls of lower importance because they have likely practiced the stall maneuvers many times,

making them confident in their abilities to deal with stalls. Overall, it appeared that the participants in this study had a good understanding of aviation safety and held opinions that were generally in line with the findings of the data.

Christian Application

As a Christian school, it is essential to prioritize safety, as the Bible instructs Christians to care for others and the environment. People cannot know what the right course of action is or what the safest option is if they do not seek out the truth and assess their own perspectives to determine if they align with it. Christians may say that they are called not to be safe, but to be confident in Christ, and this is true; it is often more dangerous by the world's standards to follow Jesus than to follow the world. However, when Christians are put in charge of people's lives, as happens when sitting at the controls of an airplane, then they are responsible for the safety of those people. As stewards of creation, it is essential to seek the truth and strive for safety.

Recommendation

This research found that flight students seem to generally have a positive and accurate view of the risks involved in flight training. However, due to the sampling population, the results are only accurately applicable to flight training at California Baptist University (CBU). Therefore, the first recommendation is that CBU continue its training in safety and maintain a focus on preventing accidents. This research also recommends that more research be conducted, specifically on Part 61 schools. To examine the safety mindset of flight students outside the collegiate atmosphere, which would yield more generalizable results.

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Appendix A

Full Survey Text

Perceived Danger in Flight Training Research Survey

1. Consent to Participate in Research **Research Title:** Perceived Dangers in Flight Training

Researcher: Benjamin J. Lemasters Tahir, CBU **Contact Information:** (213) 601 - 5034
Faculty Advisor: Dr. Prather **Purpose, Procedure, and Duration:** I am a researcher from California Baptist University, inviting you to participate in a survey. The goal of this research is to learn about the perceived dangers in flight training from those who currently participate in flight training (i.e., CFI and flight students). If you agree to participate in our study, you will be asked to answer eight survey questions, which should take no more than five minutes to complete. **Eligibility:** You must meet the following requirements to participate in this research study: You must be 18 years old or older to participate. Please only respond if you are either a flight instructor or a flight student. **Benefits:** You may not personally benefit from participating in this study, but your answers could help us gain a deeper understanding of the perceived dangers in flight training. **Risks:** There should be no risk associated with taking this survey, but if any question makes you feel uncomfortable, you can skip it. And, you can also stop the survey at any time. This survey uses Microsoft Forms to collect your responses. They may have Terms of Service and Privacy policies outside of California Baptist University's control that allow them to use your data for other purposes. You will not receive any rewards or payment for taking part in the study. **Alternative Opportunities:** We know of no alternative except not to participate in our study. **Privacy and Future Use:** Your responses to the research survey are anonymous. That means we won't know which responses are yours. We won't collect names, internet addresses, email addresses, or any other identifiable information. We may use your responses in future research or share them with other researchers. **Complaints or Concerns:** If you have questions about the study, please contact the researcher using the contact information provided above. Thank you for taking the time to consider our study. You do not have to participate in our study, but we hope you will. Please select an option below to indicate you have read this information and you wish to take the survey:

- I agree
- I do not agree

Categorizing Information

2. Where are you participating in flight training/teaching?
 - CBU
 - Other
3. Are you a Certified Flight Instructor or a Student Pilot?
 - Flight Instructor
 - Student Pilot
 - Other
5. What pilot certification are you currently pursuing?
 - Private Pilot
 - Instrument
 - Commercial
 - Other

Survey Questions

The following questions pertain specifically to incidents within flight training.

6. Rank the following in the order you think they are most likely to occur in flight training. (Drag to reorder)
 - Midair collisions
 - Loss of control on landing
 - Unintended stall (including spin)
 - Fuel mismanagement
 - Mechanical failure
7. Rank the following in the order of how dangerous you believe they would be if they were to occur (i.e., causing the most injury/fatality). (Drag to reorder)
 - Midair collisions
 - Loss of control on landing
 - Unintended stall (including spin)
 - Fuel mismanagement
 - Mechanical failure
8. Rank the following in the order of how important you believe they are to prepare for. (Drag to reorder)
 - Midair collisions
 - Loss of control on landing

- Unintended stall (including spin)
- Fuel mismanagement
- Mechanical failure

9. Do you believe accidents are more likely to occur during instructional flights or non-instructional flights (not including commercial flights)

- More likely during instructional flights
- More likely during non-instructional flights

10. Do you believe accidents are more likely to be fatal if they occur during instructional flights or non-instructional flights (not including commercial flights)

- More fatal during instructional flights
- More fatal during non-instructional flights

11. Please rate to what degree you believe a pre-flight safety self-assessment is important for the safety of flights, specifically, of self-assessments for CFIs and student pilots.

	Not at all important	Not very important	Neutral	Important	Very Important
CFI					
Student Pilot					

